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State-of-the-Art Report 3

Project: Games, Heritage, Arts, & Sport: the economic, social, and cultural value of the European video game ecosystem. GAMEHEARTS

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Executive Summary

GAMEHEARTS's third state-of-the-art report reviews how video games are shaping the cultural, social, and economic dimensions of three core sectors: museums, classical music, and sport. It explores how these domains are responding to shifts in audience expectations, the widespread adoption of digital media, and the accelerating influence of immersive and participatory technologies.

In museums, gamification and video games are increasingly integrated into exhibitions and learning environments. These tools are used to attract younger, more diverse audiences, enhance educational outcomes, and foster interactive visitor experiences. While research highlights the potential benefits of these approaches, they also raise challenges, including accessibility, sustainability, and concerns over trivialising complex subjects.

In classical music, long-standing formal traditions have historically limited experimentation with digital media. However, recent years, particularly since the COVID-19 pandemic, have seen growing openness to technologies such as real-time concert apps, virtual and augmented reality performances, and collaborations with video game soundtracks. These efforts are helping to reframe classical music as more accessible and culturally relevant to younger generations.

In sport, the shift is more advanced, driven by the rapid growth of esports, immersive broadcasting, and hybrid fan experiences. While traditionally sceptical of audience-facing technology, sport organisations are now investing in VR stadiums, metaverse platforms, and game-based fan engagement. These strategies aim to respond to falling television viewership and changing consumption habits, especially among younger fans. However, tensions remain around the dominance of digital platforms, the uneven reach of immersive tools, and the ethical implications of recent technologies.

Across all three sectors, the report finds that digital and game-based tools have the potential to enhance participation, accessibility, and cultural relevance. Yet, their success depends on thoughtful implementation, sensitivity to audience needs, and the ability to balance innovation with institutional integrity. The findings suggest that as audiences become more accustomed to digital interaction, these sectors are expected to adapt, while critically reflecting on the risks, costs, and cultural implications of doing so.

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1. PROJECT SUMMARY

GAMEHEARTS seeks to maximise the value of the European video game industry ecosystems (hereafter, EVGIE) within a wider social context of the creative and cultural industries (hereafter, CCI). This considers the importance of the EVGIE in contributing to economic growth, job creation, physical and mental wellbeing, and social and cultural cohesion, by particularly focusing on how a stronger and closer working relationship between more the traditional and emergent cultural sectors, can work better to create more inclusive and socially responsible cultural experiences. The consortium offers policy recommendations and roadmaps setting out how the EVGIE can and should develop, and where it could act as a driver for sustained innovation and economic growth. It will utilise an evidence-based approach that focuses not just on video game development, but rather adopts a holistic ecosystem approach, utilising both established (desk research, such as policy review, systematic literature review and field research like indepth and focus group interviews) and more innovative methodologies (action research using design thinking marathons), to consider the competitiveness and development of the EVGIE, and how video game know-how and technologies could drive innovation in the wider CCI. In so doing, GAMEHEARTS will develop 'ludic experiences', to explore possibilities of more inclusive, engaging, and empowering cultural experiences. Working across seven work packages the universities of Salford (UK), Tampere (Finland), Vienna (Austria), Breda University of Applied Sciences (Netherlands), and Wroclaw University of Economics and Business (Poland) will work in partnership with Ubisoft (France) and other major video game partners and associations (including the Video Games Europe & EGDF) to explore current and future trends in the EVGIE. The consortium includes some key cultural case study partners in order to explore the ways on which game-related technologies and practices are, and can be, used to increase access to heritage, the arts, and sport.

2. INTRODUCTION

This report forms part of GAMEHEARTS Work Package 6 (WP6), which examines the social, cultural, and economic value of the European video game ecosystem in relation to key domains of cultural life. Specifically, this third state-of-the-art review explores how video games and associated technologies are reshaping cultural engagement across three traditionally distinct but increasingly interconnected sectors: museums, classical music, and sport (aligning with GAMEHEARTS' cultural partners, the Imperial War Museum, the London Symphony Orchestra, and City Football Group). In particular, each sector has faced significant pressures to adapt in the face of shifting audience behaviours, widespread digitalisation, and the growing cultural importance and influence of video games.

The rationale for focusing on these three domains is grounded in their shared status as cultural touchstones - institutions and practices through which collective memory, identity, and social connection are often negotiated. Yet each has also grappled with how they remain relevant in an increasingly platformised media environment, particularly with younger audiences. In recent years, the integration of video game technologies, from gamification and interactive exhibits, to esports, and immersive environments, has become a key strategy for many cultural sectors as a way of engaging new audiences. However, these developments are not without complexity. While digital innovation promises to democratise participation and diversify cultural engagement, it can also introduce new exclusions, financial risks, and tensions around ideas, authenticity and the strategic direction of cultural institutions.

This report then serves three core aims. First, it offers a synthesis of existing industry practices and academic research on how video games and game technologies are being utilised across these sectors, highlighting both the opportunities and limits of these practices. Second, it provides comparative insights into how cultural institutions across Europe are responding to the pressures of digital transformation, with attention to the role of COVID-19 in accelerating these trends. Third, it identifies key challenges and areas of concern that must be addressed if these sectors are to adopt gaming technologies in ways that are sustainable, inclusive, and culturally meaningful.

In museums, we review the growing use of gamification and video games to attract younger and more diverse audiences, support educational outcomes, and foster interactive visitor experiences. Here, video games are increasingly viewed not only as tools for engagement but also as legitimate cultural artefacts worthy of exhibition in their own right. Yet questions persist around accessibility, curatorial integrity, and the risks of trivialising complex content.

In the classical music sector, we examine how orchestras and venues have begun to experiment with apps, AR/VR performances, and collaborations with the video game industry - notably through live concerts featuring game soundtracks. These efforts mark a tentative shift in a sector long resistant to change, offering potential pathways to reach younger audiences and dismantle barriers to participation. However, tensions remain between modernisation and tradition, particularly among established audiences.

The sport section explores the most developed and commercially driven uses of video game technologies, from esports partnerships to VR stadiums and metaverse-based fan engagement. Here, the report considers how the sports industry, particularly football, has moved from suspicion to embracing fan-facing digital media – prompted by declining television viewership and changing consumption patterns among Gen Z and younger Millennials. At the same time, the dominance of proprietary platforms, the uneven global distribution of immersive access, and the speculative nature of technologies like NFTs (non-fungible token) raise important concerns.

Taken together, these case studies provide critical insight into the evolving role of video games as both a cultural medium and a set of technological infrastructures through which public institutions are reimagining their futures. While the precise applications vary, the convergence of these sectors around game-based practices reflects a broader shift: from traditional broadcast models to participatory engagement; from singular cultural authority to co-creative interaction; and from analogue institutions to hybrid, digitally-augmented experiences.

As the GAMEHEARTS project continues to trace the impacts of the European video game ecosystem, this report contributes an essential cultural and policy-facing perspective. It informs both academic understanding and sectoral strategy, offering evidence to support more inclusive, reflexive, and sustainable uses of video game technologies in cultural life.

3. MUSEUMS, GAMIFICATION AND VIDEO GAMES

3.1 Introduction

Museums have been long considered central to cultural industries worldwide. In recent years, museums have faced a complex mix of challenges and opportunities stemming from rapid technological advancements, changing visitor expectations, and global disruptions. Although primarily seen as physical spaces for preservation and display, museums are increasingly reimagined as dynamic, interactive and hybrid environments. As described by Camps-Ortueta et al. (2021), “The goal of museums is no longer just to build a large collection, but above all to formulate a story in collaboration with visitors and communities” (p. 194). As such, museums adopt digital technologies and innovations to make their offerings more accessible, engaging, educational and entertaining (Raimo et al., 2022).

Museums’ approach to technology and digital media was significantly reevaluated during the COVID-19 pandemic and the lockdowns that followed. Museums had to quickly adapt while striving to stay relevant and offer comfort and security during a time of uncertainty and isolation. This urgency drove the accelerated development and adoption of digital initiatives. Many museums and heritage sites launched virtual tours, online exhibitions, and expanded their social media presence, enabling audiences to “travel from home” while traditional tourism remained on hold (Raimo et al., 2022; Sánchez-Amboage et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2024). When restrictions eased and cultural life resumed by late 2021, it became clear that many of these digital strategies would remain integral to museums’ long-term practices (ibid).

As museums increasingly adopt digital technologies, many have embraced video games either as standalone exhibits or as interactive features that enhance engagement with traditional displays (Camps-Ortueta et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2024). These developments prompted critical questions about how museums can balance educational goals, cultural significance, and digital innovation while remaining relevant, inclusive, and sustainable. Given this, in the following review, we explore the use of video games and gamification in museums, highlighting their potential benefits and challenges.

3.2 Video Games and Gamified Objects in Museums

Museums have increasingly turned to video game exhibitions to engage groups that are often underrepresented in museum spaces, such as young people and men, as part of broader efforts to diversify their audiences (Carlsson, 2020; Barron & Leask, 2017; Zhang et al., 2024). These exhibitions affirm the cultural value of games and contribute to their legitimacy (Gislam et al., 2025; Naskali et al., 2013). For example, in 2018, London’s Victoria and Albert Museum (V&A) presented Videogames: Design/Play/Disrupt, an exhibition exploring game design and cultural impact through games and related materials like developer diaries and sketchbooks. This aligned with the V&A’s mission to celebrate design and inspire creativity

(V&A, 2024, para.1). Similarly, the Imperial War Museums' (IWM) War Games: Real Conflicts | Virtual Worlds | Extreme Entertainment (2022–2023) examined how war is portrayed in video games and called it “the UK’s first exhibition” to tackle this subject (IWM, 2022, para.2). Alongside such exhibitions, dedicated video game museums have also emerged, including Berlin’s Computerspielemuseum (1997), Moscow’s Museum of Soviet Arcade Machines (2007), Sheffield’s National Videogame Museum (2018), and Kyoto’s Nintendo Museum (2024).

Other examples, and perhaps more common, are the inclusion of video games in museums through gamification (the presentation of objects, exhibits and artefacts using game-like features). For example, IWM showcases the Enigma machine that was used to encrypt and decrypt communications during World War II. Alongside the actual machine, visitors are encouraged to play a short game on a touch screen that explains how the Enigma was created and gives them the opportunity to crack a code themselves. In another case, the Louvre offers a Nintendo 3DS Guide that includes quizzes, maps and interactive content that users can engage with on-site as well as in the comfort of their homes. These museums and many more offer gamified, interactive and immersive experiences since, as Naskali et al argue (2013), “Audiences want to do something other than just looking at and reading about things” (p. 232). Such audiences, usually younger generations, have already become accustomed to digital devices and interactivity and therefore expect these to be included in the cultural venues they frequent (Barron & Leask, 2017; Raimo et al., 2022). According to Çetin and Erbay (2021), gamification in museums has the potential to offer four kinds of experiences and purposes: (1) educational - help people learn new things; (2) entertainment - help people have a good time; (3) art - help people appreciate beauty; (4) escape - help people escape from everyday life. Moreover, they argue, gamification in museums does not only foster engagement between the visitor and the object or the museum, but it can also contribute to visitors engaging more with each other.

3.3 Edutainment: Negotiating Museums’ Educational Role

A substantial amount of scholarship on gamification in museums has been dedicated to its integral role of fostering learning among children (and adults) through play (Camps-Ortueta et al., 2021; Kidd, 2015; Nofal et al., 2020; Xu & Fagan, 2023; Zhang et al., 2024). According to different scholars, gamification moves beyond passive knowledge transmission by fostering agency and curiosity in visitors. This approach is grounded in the notion that children learn better through play and games (Camps-Ortueta, et al., 2021; Kidd, 2015; Zhang et al., 2024). As Zhang et al. (2024) note, gamified experiences can transform visitors “From cultural observers to cultural interactors and producers” (p. 3). This approach is particularly evident in the use of augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) in heritage sites and museums, where immersive digital environments allow users to explore reconstructed historical scenes and

engage with cultural narratives (Xu & Fagan, 2023; Zhang et al., 2024). While museums already offer tangible connections to the past, it is argued that AR and VR deepen this experience by enabling real-time interaction with rich, multisensory content. These technologies are not limited to historical interpretation; they also help explain abstract artistic concepts in art museums (Bossavit et al., 2018) and support multisensory learning in science museums (Zhou et al., 2022).

Within the context of gamified educational tools, the concept of “serious games” stands out. Unlike traditional commercial games, serious games are designed with purposes beyond entertainment - they aim to educate, train, or influence players in meaningful ways. By combining engaging gameplay with educational material, serious games can promote and deepen one’s knowledge on a specific topic, support skill development and promote a possible behavioural change (Bogost, 2007; Djaouti et al., 2011). For instance, Zhang et al. (2024) recently conducted a systematic review of 24 studies that examine different gamification methods in museums that were used for educational purposes. In their review, the authors found that educational games in museums enhance knowledge sharing, enrich visitor experiences, and support informal learning. In a different example, Nofal et al. (2020) developed and evaluated TouchTomb, a gamified installation aimed at enhancing cultural learning and promoting engagement and collaboration among young museum visitors. Set in the Museum of Art and History in Brussels, the setup included a life-sized replica of an ancient Egyptian tomb-chapel wall, a shared progress bar, and three spatially distinct games. Based on a study of 190 pupils aged 10-14 across 14 school visits, the researchers found that the gamified instalment enhanced children’s cultural learning and fostered a sense of engagement and collaboration. Similar findings have emerged from other studies showing that gamified objects and activities in museums can also increase interest among older visitors, which can potentially contribute to a deeper learning experience (Camps-Ortueta et al., 2021; Barron & Leask, 2017).

The somewhat rigid distinction between games “for fun” and games “for learning”, fostered by some academics and museum personnel alike, has contributed to the perception of museums as spaces of “edutainment”, where education and entertainment converge to foster engagement (Barron & Leask, 2017; Xu & Fagan, 2023). This framing challenges traditional and, perhaps more conservative, expectations that require museums to maintain a strict educational integrity, using video games and gamification solely as tools for delivering knowledge (Camps-Ortueta et al., 2021). Although, as Hanquinet and Savage (2012) argue audiences still see visiting museums as a kind of “educative leisure” (p. 42), consequently the educative aspect remains important to museums if they want to compete with other leisure and cultural attractions.

3.4 Pushback and Challenges of Gamification in Museums

Alongside the seemingly positive reception of the inclusion of video games in museums, there has also been negative feedback and critique. Despite the growing number of video game exhibitions across Europe and beyond, it is still unclear whether they have truly legitimised video games as cultural artefacts or increased museums' popularity. For example, McMaster (2023) conducted a six-month ethnography at the V&A during its video games exhibition and found that, despite the positive reviews, attendance was significantly lower than expected. McMaster argues that after the exhibition ended, the museum shied away from engaging with video games again, and the curator in charge subsequently left the organisation. Additionally, the inclusion of video games in museum settings has sparked criticism, particularly in the popular press. Jones (2012), for example, objected to the MoMA's decision to include video games in its collection, arguing that they are not art. As a different critic suggested, video games are often perceived as childish and simplistic, associated with formulaic gameplay and lowbrow narratives, an image that makes them incompatible with the perceived cultural status of museums (Carlsson, 2020). Lastly, MacDonald (2018) highlighted that the inclusion of video games in museums holds an inherent tension between display and interaction. As MacDonald notes, "The soul of games – the thing that gives them their power – is interactivity, the chance to be a participant, rather than an observer. This is the very thing that's taken away when they are placed in a museum, where they can be seen and read about – but not played" (MacDonald, para. 1, 2018). Thus, museums must find ways to attract audiences while balancing the interactive appeal of video games with the need to maintain their credibility and avoid appearing merely as arcades (Bagnall et al., 2024).

The inclusion of video games in museums has also been facing other challenges and setbacks that warrant attention. One persistent issue is the "playwall", the barriers that discourage audiences from engaging with video games and their interfaces (Yodovich et al., 2025). Ian Kikuchi, Senior Curator of the IWM's War Games, highlighted the difficulty of integrating video games into museums, noting the need to keep these organisations accessible to visitors with diverse physical and cognitive needs (Bagnall et al., 2024). Developers must consider cognitive abilities, learning styles, and personal interests, while carefully calibrating tutorials, content difficulty, and interface design that will appeal to as wider audience as possible (Zhang et al., 2024; Çetin & Erbay, 2021). When these elements are not adequately addressed, visitors may feel excluded and disengage from parts of the exhibition.

Another common logistical issue involves reliance on visitors' personal devices and maintenance. Some gamified experiences require visitors to use their own smartphones (to scan QR codes, for instance), assuming not only that the devices are compatible and functional, but also that users are able to access stable internet connections, often via unreliable public Wi-Fi (Raimo et al., 2022; Bagnall et al., 2013). Even when connectivity is available, these experiences must remain short and straightforward, as many visitors lack the

time or patience for extended interactions (Barron & Leask, 2017). Moreover, the cost and effort of developing and maintaining digital, gamified tools can be prohibitive, particularly given how quickly technology becomes obsolete. Therefore, many museum games have a short lifespan, either because they remain confined to research contexts or because updating and maintaining them is too resource-intensive (Camps-Ortueta et al., 2021; Connor, 2025). This is compounded by the fact that museum exhibits often travel or change, while games built around them tend to be built to a specification for a particular layout or context, making adaptation difficult.

Although studies have highlighted the educational potential of gamification in museums, its actual effectiveness has been questioned by some scholars. For instance, Sangmuang et al. (2025) found that while VR can enhance the entertainment value of educational experiences, it does not offer a significant advantage over non-gamified alternatives. Similarly, Aitamurto et al. (2018) argued that immersive tools may create an illusion of learning without necessarily fostering deeper educational outcomes. For example, Schultz (2023) examined interactive exhibitions at the National Holocaust Centre in Nottingham and the V&A, called The Forever Project, where visitors could interact with digital recordings of real Holocaust survivors. The exhibition aimed to preserve survivor testimonies beyond their lifetimes and allow visitors to ask questions to their digital avatars. The creators hoped this would foster greater empathy toward the survivors and allow visitors to learn history through a “firsthand” witness. In practice, Schultz found the experience to be clunky: pre-recorded answers often failed to align with visitors’ questions, resulting in a disjointed and inauthentic conversational flow; moreover, Schultz argued, these virtual witness experiences might have inhibited empathy and learning. Due to the gamified elements association with play and entertainment, many visitors tested the limits of the technology by interacting with the avatars in unintended, sometimes flippant, ways. In addition, the vocal prompts used to trigger responses from the digital witnesses led visitors to treat them like virtual assistants (such as Siri) rather than respectfully, as equals. Thus, despite the intended purposes of certain interactive objects, visitor engagement with them can be unpredictable (Bagnall et al., 2013). Moreover, perhaps not all educational or cultural activities lend themselves to gamification, and even when they do, such approaches do not guarantee deeper learning.

Thus, museums have been seemingly under the pressure to become more gamified and offer more digitally innovative forms to visitors to engage with their exhibits. These efforts are sometimes celebrated and embraced, while other research has revealed the continuous challenges of including video games and gamification within a museum setting. Such issues are also present in our following case study, classical music venues.

4. CLASSICAL MUSIC, VIDEO GAMES, AND DIGITAL MEDIA

4.1 Introduction

In recent decades, classical music venues have navigated an evolving cultural landscape. They have faced changing audience expectations, shifting patterns of engagement and a decline in classical music education. While the genre's rich history and artistic value remain widely celebrated, traditional concert formats and programming have not always aligned with growing interest in digital and immersive media. Social and digital developments have prompted many orchestras to explore new approaches that broaden their appeal while remaining true to their core identity. In the following review, we examine such challenges and the technological solutions used by different musical venues to draw new audiences. In particular, this review engages with the intersection of video games and video games tech with classical music venues.

4.2 Barriers in Classical Music Engagement

Over the years, scholars have observed changes in classical music engagement (Crawford et al., 2014; Dobson, 2010; Frantz, 2015; RNCM, 2024). One key factor is younger audiences, who traditionally seek more visually stimulating and participatory experiences than traditional concert formats offer (Kolb, 2000; Brown, 2004). This generational shift contrasts sharply with the ritualised, formal culture of classical music. Small (1987), for instance, equated classical music performances to a Catholic mass, where strict conventions of behaviour are enforced, resulting in the potential alienation of newcomers who are unfamiliar with these traditions. In a study conducted by Kolb (2000) young attendees experience anxiety over their lack of cultural capital or "special knowledge," further deterring them from engaging with the art form. According to Kolb, "people have many choices on how to spend their leisure time and may not be willing to spend this learning more about culture" (2000, p. 55).

In contrast to the gatekeeping of classical music, Frantz (2015) suggests, concertgoers search for more relaxed, engaging and social experiences. The lack of socialising between audience members, or between the audience and the performers in classical music venues, further can potentially lead to a sense of disengagement and alienation. Financial constraints further exacerbate these challenges, as orchestras often become risk-averse, favouring nostalgic programs centred on well-known historical composers. This trend stagnates the repertoire and leaves little room for contemporary voices, which could invigorate the genre and attract audiences seeking fresh and relevant content (Frantz, 2015). As Botstein (1996) notes, the concert hall risks becoming a "museum" of past greatness, disconnected from the dynamic cultural landscape of the present. Thus, without addressing these barriers, venues can be perceived as gated, old-fashioned and reinforcing class boundaries rather than fostering inclusivity, accessibility and innovation.

Despite these challenges, there are signs of opportunity, optimism and potential change. A 2023 report from the Royal Philharmonic Orchestra found that one in four people under 35 expressed an interest in exploring orchestral music. This report suggests that by embracing innovative programming, leveraging technology, and reimagining the concert experience as more inclusive and participatory, venues can address these barriers and create pathways for future engagement. Indeed, efforts to adapt have included initiatives like casual “jeans and beer” concerts, relaxed performances tailored for people with disabilities, performances in public spaces, and incorporating mainstream genres like film scores and pop arrangements into programming (Sigurjonsson, 2010). A successful example of these initiatives is the London Symphony Orchestra’s Half Six Fix: early evening concerts that are shorter and more relaxed, featuring live introductions from conductors and musicians. Research conducted for LSO in 2022 found that younger audiences particularly prefer this kind of performance rather than longer and more “traditional” ones (Morris Hargreaves McIntyre, 2022). Additionally, the integration of technology and digital media, such as digital streaming has offered new avenues for engagement and drawing in new and younger audiences (Hernández, 2023; Millers, 2024).

Having recognised the potential for drawing new audiences, we move on to review examples of efforts made by classical music venues to appeal to a variety of audiences through digital media innovations.

4.3 Digital Media in Classical Music Venues: Case Studies

In the past three decades, more effort has been put on incorporating technology and digital media into classical music venues. An earlier example of this is the hand-held electronic device, Concert Companion (CoCo), that was used in several concert halls in the UK in the late 90s and early 00s (Brown 2024). CoCo was used to provide information for audiences to read and learn more about the performers, music and composers, during the live event. More recently, The BBC Philharmonic 2019-2020 season in Manchester introduced an app called Notes which sends audience members information to their smartphones in real time during performances. Notes users were seated in a designated, separate section of the hall to avoid distracting audience members who preferred not to use the app. In an article published about the new app, the BBC described the device as a technology that “may help re-invigorate people’s interest in live classical music” (Bootle, 2019, n.p).

Several venues have also used VR and AR technology to offer a more immersive experience to their audience and gain more traction. The VR opera *Weltatem* that premiered in the Netherlands (Avraam, 2018) is one example. This project explored the artistic potentials of VR technology: enhancing classical music performances through visualisation while empowering the audience by shifting its role from passive spectatorship to active participation. In *Weltatem*,

the audience was divided into two groups: one immersed in the VR experience, encouraged to sing alongside professional musicians in the physical space, and the other serving as a witnessing audience. Midway through the performance, these roles were reversed. The witnessing audience played a significant role by observing the interaction between musicians and VR participants, with the helmets doubling as theatrical props. This arrangement created a dynamic array of perspectives and lines-of-sight, offering a rich and multifaceted experience of the concert. In the UK, the Philharmonia Orchestra has created five VR experiences since 2014 showcasing music of the likes of Beethoven, Mahler and Tchaikovsky. More recently, a new startup called OPUS is currently seeking to revolutionise live performances by transforming them into holographic experiences via a smartphone or tablet. OPUS will allow any real-world location to become a stage as audiences can immerse themselves in performances, interact with holograms from every angle, and adjust their scale (Beyond, 2024).

Such examples of VR and AR usage could also be understood as part of the growing intersection of classical music and video games. One clear example for this is the various projects of orchestras playing video game music, such as the Game Music Foundation, The Sound of Gaming and Final Symphony (whose first performance was hosted by the London Symphony Orchestra). Such projects perform world-wide promoting the music of video games as a legitimate form of art and making classical music more accessible to newer audiences. The rise in live performances of video game music has been driven by younger audiences, as indicated by the Royal Philharmonic Orchestra survey (2023). In the survey, it was found that people under the age of 35 were more likely to enjoy concerts featuring film/musicals (34%), or pop/rock crossover (22%) than a Mozart or Beethoven performance (19%). More specifically, the survey saw an increase of people interested in attending performances of video game music, from 4% in 2018 to 11% in 2022. A reason for a crossover interest in attending concerts, according to Frantz (2015), is that audiences are more interested in listening to music they have already formed a connection with rather than listening to something new and unfamiliar. Many video games employ an orchestral soundtrack, either composing something new (The Last of Us, The Legend of Zelda series, Angry Birds) or incorporating already produced works (Bioshock, The Evil Within, Kingdom Hearts). As such, fans of these games have built a connection with this music, which provides more reason to attend a classical music concert which crosses over with video games (Gibbons, 2018). To emphasise fan association, these concerts often contextualise the music with edited footage from the game connected with the piece, often highlighting a heightened emotional moment from the game's narrative. Examples include the NeiR Orchestra Concert, Game On, and PlayStation: The Concert.

The Royal Philharmonic Orchestra survey also addressed video games specifically and argued that video games are a clear cultural influence for children. Overall, 18% of children said they listened to orchestral music as a soundtrack to a video game. Furthermore, the influence of games starts early: around 15% of children aged between 6-11 said video games introduced them to orchestral music – a sign of how influential video games are in giving

young people a connection to the genre. Indeed, video games have become a platform for musical engagement. For instance, Breese et al. (2020) noted that online games such as Fortnite hold live music events where artists debut their new albums. In a different example, Kylie et al. (2011) argued that games such as Guitar Hero and Rock Band inspire young people's interest in music and picking up a musical instrument. While critics argue that such games cannot replace the nuances of mastering live instruments, Kylie et al. argue that they effectively introduce fundamental music concepts and encourage further exploration of formal music practices. Lastly, and more recently, the University of Manchester and the University of York launched an online interactive digital opera. The opera, *Black Fell*, is inspired by visits to the Kielder Observatory in Northumberland and is described as a "game-for-music" that tells a story in song. The project combines musical and a poetic narrative, offering a new approach to opera storytelling by incorporating elements of gaming (Black Fell, 2023). Examples such as these demonstrate the power of video games as influential platforms that can expose young people to a variety of musical genres.

4.4 Digital Media in Classical Music: Opportunities and Challenges

Efforts to integrate technology into classical music concerts have shown mixed results, revealing both opportunities and significant challenges. The Concert Companion device, for instance, received initial positive feedback from early users (Brown, 2004). However, its adoption was hindered by high costs for orchestras to purchase and maintain the devices, the labour-intensive process of creating unique commentary for each concert, and a polarised audience response (Frantz, 2015). While some concertgoers appreciated the added insights, others found the embedded notifications disruptive, reflecting broader resistance to changing the traditional concert experience. In a 2015 interview, Roland Valliere, the creator of the companion, explained that the device was too costly for most orchestras to adopt at the time. He further noted that the companion was ahead of its time as it was introduced before the rise and prominence of social media (MacNamara, 2015).

In general, attempts to modernise classical music concerts often face pushback from loyal audiences. For example, O'Sullivan (2009) found that older audiences acknowledged the need to attract younger attendees but strongly opposed altering established traditions. Thus, initiatives like themed concert titles were dismissed as "crass" by some participants, underscoring the cultural divide and tension between preserving tradition and embracing change. In a different case, the London Symphony Orchestra¹ found that their audience app, EnCue, received the lowest ratings of any element of the concert. When offered both printed and digital versions of their programme, audience members at the LSO favoured the printed version across all ages.

Despite challenges raised in previous studies and reports, we argue that the current cultural climate presents an opportunity for the digitisation of classical music to succeed. This possibility is primarily due to changes in cultural consumption since the COVID-19 pandemic and the ever-growing omnipresence of digital media in the past two decades. The COVID-19 pandemic, and the lockdowns and restrictions that were enforced because of it, were a moment of crisis, but also of change and opportunities. Due to the closure of cultural venues and the need for social distancing, musicians and organisations had to find new avenues to promote their music. Musicians turned to digital media to maintain their connection with audiences, often through live-streamed performances (Bayle & Provenzano, 2021; Breese et al., 2020; Phillips & Krause, 2024). While some of these efforts were born out of necessity, they accelerated a preexisting trend of digital integration within the music industry, paving the way for a broader shift in audience engagement strategies (ibid). Initiatives like the Berliner Philharmoniker's Digital Concert Hall allowed global audiences to access performances, however high subscription costs hindered broader adoption (Bayle & Provenzano, 2021). Despite these barriers, audience interest in digital cultural offerings grew significantly, as audiences have become more accustomed to using their laptops and smartphones to engage with music, even among age groups that were less used to doing so before (Janssen et al., 2021). Surveys indicate that engagement with digital content in general more than doubled post-lockdown, with many expressing openness to continued virtual interactions in the future (Massey, 2021). The transition to digital formats has also reshaped perceptions of accessibility and inclusivity in classical music. Streaming platforms have helped overcome traditional barriers, such as the formal atmosphere of concert halls, allowing new audiences to explore classical music from the comfort of their homes.

5. LIVE SPORT, GAME TECHNOLOGIES, AND IMMERSIVE EXPERIENCES

5.1 Introduction

This section provides a review of the evolving relationship between live sport and digital media, with a particular focus on emerging immersive technologies such as virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and metaverse platforms. It examines how these innovations are reshaping fan engagement, not by replacing traditional practices, but by extending them into new, interactive and multi-platform domains, and how the sports industry is responding to shifting audience expectations. Drawing on academic literature and current industry practice, the section traces sport's historical ambivalence toward audience-facing technologies, the recent acceleration in immersive fan experiences, and the challenges posed by platformisation, media fragmentation, and speculative technologies like NFTs. Here, football serves as the primary case study, but the analysis reflects wider developments across elite sport globally.

5.2 COVID-19 and the Evolving Nature of Audience Engagement

Much like with museums and musical venues, the COVID-19 pandemic significantly disrupted professional sport, curtailing live events and rendering traditional modes of fan engagement temporarily inaccessible. In the context of football, matches were suspended or played behind closed doors, and many of the spatial, sensory, and social rituals associated with fandom, particularly physical attendance, were abruptly interrupted. However, rather than resulting in the erosion of fan attachment, this period marked a reconfiguration of the modalities through which football fandom was enacted.

Crawford et al. (2022) examine this reconfiguration through a study of football-themed digital content consumption during the first UK lockdown. Their findings identify how fans engaged with a range of alternative digital practices, such as rewatching archival footage, participating in online football-related trivia, utilising social media, and turning to video games such as FIFA, to sustain a sense of continuity and a connection to the sport. These practices, while technologically-mediated and often asynchronous, were nonetheless emotionally resonant and socially meaningful. As the authors argue, they constituted affective and embodied engagements that enabled fans to navigate the absence of live football by forging new forms of connection and routine.

The capacity for such a pivot was underpinned by football's existing media infrastructure and its embeddedness within platformed digital ecologies. Clubs and media organisations rapidly mobilised content archives, interactive formats, and remote fan initiatives. Simultaneously, supporters themselves created and shared content, such as memes, commentary videos, and simulated matches, which collectively reproduced aspects of the matchday experience. These developments highlight the adaptability of fandom in times of disruption and illustrate how digital practices can sustain both personal and collective identities linked to football (Crawford et al., 2022).

Although COVID-related restrictions have now all but disappeared, many of the practices adopted during this period have persisted and, in some cases, become further embedded within the cultural economy posing new opportunities and challenges. In the following review, we examine the historical connection between sports and technology and the ways in which it was embraced and rejected throughout the years.

5.3 The Uneven Relationship Between Technology and Sport

The relationship between sport and technology has been long and significant though far from uniform. Across history, sport has selectively embraced technological innovation, particularly where it enhances athletic performance, safety, and training; however, the adoption of such technologies is shaped by complex cultural narratives around fairness, authenticity, and tradition.

Even in ancient times, athletes benefited from technical improvements, for example, the design of javelins or discus in Greek athletics. In modern sport, materials science and biomechanics have driven substantial change. Innovations such as synthetic running tracks, carbon-fibre tennis rackets, or aerodynamic cycling gear have redefined the limits of performance (Guttmann, 1978). Similarly, training technologies, including GPS tracking, motion analysis, and heart-rate monitoring, are now embedded in elite sport environments (Carling, Reilly, & Williams, 2009; James, 2013).

In football, for example, positional data and biometric feedback from systems like Catapult or STATSports are now used to monitor player load, manage injury risk, and analyse tactical patterns. These technologies have been widely accepted because they align with existing values around preparation and performance enhancement.

Such acceptance is not universal. Some sports, particularly those with strong cultural traditions, such as cricket or boxing, have been slower to integrate technology, often citing concerns over the erosion of human judgement or the “spirit” of the game (Miah, 2004). The delayed introduction of goal-line technology in football, despite clear evidence of its potential benefits, highlights this tension.

More broadly, questions around the legitimacy of technologically-enhanced performance, including debates about prosthetics, gene editing, and data-driven decision-making, raise important ethical and philosophical issues. As Mann et al. (2007) note, even perceptual-cognitive skills are increasingly shaped by technologically mediated environments, challenging traditional ideas of “natural” athletic talent.

5.4 Sport's Suspicion of Audience-Facing Technologies

While sport has often embraced new technologies to improve performance, training, and officiating, it has traditionally been much more reluctant to adopt innovations aimed at engaging fans. Football in particular has a long history of viewing new media technologies with suspicion, often fearing they would undermine live attendance, disrupt existing revenue streams, or distract future generations of supporters.

This caution was especially evident in football's early relationship with television. Although the technical capacity to broadcast live matches existed from the mid-twentieth century, the Football League and clubs resisted widespread live television coverage of matches well into the 1980s. As there were deep concerns that televising games would reduce gate receipts and dilute the sanctity of the in-stadium experience (Lawrence and Crawford, 2019). And despite the increasing presence of highlight shows, live coverage of English football remained rare until the formation of the Premier League in 1992.

Football's suspicion extended beyond television. As Lawrence and Crawford (2019) outline, football's governing bodies and institutional cultures long viewed video games as a significant threat to football rather than an ally. There was a widespread perception that digital games were diverting children away from real-world sport, offering screen-based forms of engagement that disrupted traditional routes into participation and fandom. Video games were associated with sedentary lifestyles and declining youth involvement, and were often positioned in opposition to the physical, social, and local dimensions of football.

This is especially striking given that sport has been foundational to the video games industry. Some of the earliest and most influential games, such as Tennis for Two (1958) and Pong (1972), were based directly on sport. These games helped to establish the interactive entertainment industry, with sport as a central and popular theme of many early video games.

Yet despite these anxieties, it is clear that sport has been good for new media technologies. In the case of television, football eventually became a driving force behind the commercial success of satellite broadcasting. The 1992 deal between the Premier League and BSkyB is widely acknowledged as a turning point in both sporting and media history. The popularity of live football helped Sky TV expand its subscriber base and reshape the UK broadcasting landscape. And sport, and in particular football, continues to be very popular and profitable for television companies.

Similarly, sport has been central to the continued growth of the video games industry. Titles such as EA Sport FC (formerly FIFA), eFootball (originally Pro Evolution Soccer), and Football Manager (known as Championship Manager until 2005) have consistently ranked among the best-selling and most played games globally. Here it is clear that football's cultural legitimacy has helped to elevate these titles beyond entertainment, positioning them as part of how fans learn about teams, tactics, and players (Crawford & Gosling, 2009).

5.5 Sport's Embrace of Technological Fan Engagement

After decades of suspicion, sport has in recent years increasingly turned toward digital innovation to engage new audiences and expand the boundaries of fan participation. This shift is particularly visible in the rise of esports and the adoption of immersive technologies, including virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and 360-degree video, to craft new, digitally native experiences for audiences.

This change is driven in part by a marked shift in audience behaviour. For example, while most major league football clubs continue to fill stadiums, television viewership has slipped significantly. During the 2024-25 season, English Premier League matches on Sky Sports saw a 10% decline in average viewership, while TNT Sports, which broadcast 52 matches, had a 17% reduction in its year-on-year figures (Coates, 2025). In the US, NBC's average viewership of the English football Premier League dropped by approximately 7% year on year (Ministry of Sport, 2025). Meanwhile, in women's football, mainstream television audiences for the Women's Super League (WSL) declined by 35% for the 2024-25 season (Taylor, 2025).

These trends suggest that fans, especially younger generations, are no longer consuming football in the same ways that they once did. As Sebastian Carmichael-Brown, commercial director of Hashtag United, explains: "They're [football fans] not coming home from school or work and turning the television on anymore, they're putting their gaming stations on or coming online and watching YouTube" (Jenkins, 2017). For example, a recent Nielsen Sports report (2022) suggested that around 31% of Gen Z watch sport while simultaneously playing online video games, and that nearly half engage with social media (43%) or use other mobile apps (46%) during matches. This then highlights the increasingly multi-tasked and interactive nature of contemporary media consumption.

Changing consumption habits are also reflected in the rise of unofficial streaming. A 2017 BBC poll found that over one-third of Premier League fans were regularly watching matches through illegal streams – a figure likely to be much higher now. For example, a recent report by Enders Analysis suggested that football and other premium TV was being pirated on an "industrial scale" (Fraser, 2025). Together, these shifts undermine traditional broadcast models and intensify the need for football to diversify its fan engagement strategies.

One such response has been a turn to esports. As Lawrence and Crawford (2019) explain, many football clubs now operate dedicated esports divisions. Manchester City, for instance, entered competitive FIFA esports in 2016 and has since partnered with FaZe Clan to expand its digital brand across games and platforms.

This embrace of gaming and immersive media has been echoed across the sports industry. Keith Pelley, CEO of the PGA European Tour, remarked, "we are not in 1940 now, this is a time when things are changing rapidly, and technology is driving the consumption of content". He added, "it is all about engagement and it is all about not being passive, especially with

the younger generation” (Ingle, 2017). His comments encapsulate a growing recognition that traditional models of broadcast and in-person attendance must adapt - not just to new technologies, but to changing audience expectations.

Substantial investment has also gone into immersive platforms that simulate or enhance the live match experience. The idea of a “virtual stadium”, where fans can digitally attend matches as if seated in the arena, has emerged as a kind of holy grail for the sports industry. It addresses two long-standing challenges: the physical limits of stadium capacity, and the emotional inadequacy of television as a proxy for live presence. As Lawrence and Crawford (2019) note, while watching matches at home or in pubs can offer some shared pleasures, many fans still regard it as a pale substitute for “the real thing”.

The NBA pioneered immersive sports, offering weekly VR game livestreams via Meta Quest through Xtadium (2022) and Horizon Worlds (2021). These broadcasts include multi-angle viewing, spatial audio, and interactive features intended to simulate courtside immersion (Watch.NBA.com, 2023). As Marsilio, then VP of Global Media Distribution for the NBA, reflected, maybe optimistically, “we could bring that feeling of being in the arena to fans around the world” (Raymond, 2017). Other US leagues have followed suit, for example, the NFL launched the NFL Pro Era game on Meta Quest and offered player-perspective VR content via ESPN (Orlovsky, 2024), the MLB debuted the Virtual Ballpark in 2023, enabling avatars, virtual watch parties, and social zones (MLB, 2023), and Cosm has created shared-reality dome venues in Los Angeles and Dallas for 12K-resolution broadcasts of NBA, NFL, UFC, and Premier League matches (Levy, 2024). Similarly, Real Salt Lake introduced a metaverse pilot in collaboration with Boom Interactive (Real Salt Lake, 2023). UFC’s Fight Pass VR extends cage-side 180-degree viewing and gamified social experiences through Meta (Meta, 2023). Additionally, the NFL opened an official store in Roblox in 2021, enabling fan/avatar interactions across team-branded spaces (WHU, 2021). And in international tennis, Wimbledon, the Australian Open, and US Open have hosted Roblox mini-worlds and eChamps events in social-simulation games, cumulatively attracting over 17 million visits (FT, 2024).

We have also seen the start of similar innovation in English professional football. Most notably, Manchester City has expanded its digital outreach, such as through their Virtual Etihad Stadium, developed in partnership with Sony. This offers fans a 3D space for avatar-based interaction and immersive match highlights and virtual stadium tours (Mancity.com, 2024; BeyondGames.biz, 2024). Additionally, Manchester City have also launched the Blue Moon experience on Roblox, which features, Moonball minigames, Trophy Tours, avatar rewards, and significant engagement.

Similarly, other football clubs and leagues across Europe have also ventured into virtual worlds. For example, Arsenal now offers a virtual stadium tour of the Emirates Stadium on web and mobile platforms (Arsenal FC, 2024). While FC Barcelona launched branded avatar bundles in Roblox as early as 2019 and is preparing broader Roblox and Fortnite activities as part of its Barça Games and metaverse strategy (FC Barcelona, 2019; Forbes, 2025).

More widely across Europe, football's immersive evolution is also being significantly shaped by the actions of governing bodies and leagues such as UEFA, the DFL (Bundesliga), and La Liga. For example, UEFA has made substantial investments in fan-facing digital innovation through its long-term partnership with Atos, which began in 2022. This partnership underpins their Football Service Platform, which delivers real-time match data, immersive app features, and live VR content across major tournaments, including UEFA's EURO tournament and the Nations League Finals (UEFA, 2024a). In addition, UEFA's Champions Innovate programme and Innovation Hub have supported several pilot projects, including virtual trophy tours and immersive fan activations, aimed at enhancing digital fan experience on a global scale (UEFA, 2024b).

The DFL (German Bundesliga) has been particularly pioneering in immersive broadcasting. In 2025, the DFL and VfB Stuttgart trialled a 10K-resolution, 360-degree stereoscopic VR live stream of a match, offering users dynamic, multi-angle viewing and a stadium-like experience via VR headsets (DFL, 2025a). The league has also worked with Vodafone, AWS, and Immersiv.io to develop augmented reality overlays – using smart glasses to display real-time player statistics, replays, and tactical visualisations, trialled during events like the German Supercup (DFL, 2025b; Immersiv.io, 2023).

Meanwhile, La Liga has developed a digital engagement ecosystem through its technology spinoff, Sportian (formerly La Liga Tech). This includes platforms for streaming, gamification, and AI-driven fan personalisation (La Liga, 2023). Its strategic partnership with Microsoft Azure enables the delivery of scalable, cloud-based fan experiences such as chatbots, fantasy football tools, and hyper-personalised notifications (Microsoft, 2022). La Liga has also launched NFT-based digital collectibles in collaboration with Dapper Labs, allowing fans to own and trade officially licensed video highlights, similar to NBA Top Shot, and has integrated these assets into broader immersive strategies including VR and AR fan tools (Dapper Labs, 2021).

However, the long-term viability of such projects remains uncertain. The UK Culture, Media and Sport Committee (2023) has warned that fan-facing Web3 initiatives, including NFTs, may pose financial risks to supporters, particularly where speculative value is emphasised over cultural or experiential engagement.

As Nieborg and Poell (2021) argue, developments in digital engagement must be situated within the broader framework of platformisation, a process through which cultural production, distribution, and consumption are increasingly governed by the infrastructures and business models of digital platforms. These platforms, such as YouTube, Twitch, Roblox, and Meta, do not simply host content; they actively shape what is visible, how audiences interact, and what forms of participation are encouraged or monetised. This restructuring has significant implications for cultural sectors, including sport, where fan engagement is no longer confined to physical venues or linear broadcast media, but is instead shaped by algorithmic curation, user-generated content, and multi-modal interaction across interconnected digital environments.

6. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This report has explored the evolving intersections between video games, digital media, in three distinct cultural arenas: museums, classical music, and sport. Across these sectors, the integration of digital technologies, particularly gamification and immersive platforms and tools, has been marked by both innovation and ambivalence. While such tools are often framed as essential for engaging new audiences, particularly younger and more digitally native groups, they also raise enduring questions around tradition, legitimacy, accessibility, and long-term sustainability.

In museums, the adoption of video games and gamification has opened new avenues for learning, participation, and interactivity. These tools have helped reframe the museum not merely as a site of preservation, but as a space for public engagement and interactivity. From immersive VR reconstructions to touchscreen puzzles and handheld guides, museums are experimenting with ways to stimulate curiosity, collaboration, and creativity; however, this shift has not been without challenges. Concerns about trivialising serious content, technical obsolescence, accessibility barriers, and the cost of development persist. As some scholars observed, gamified approaches do not automatically guarantee deeper learning or empathy and may even provoke unpredictable behaviours, particularly when the line between entertainment and education becomes blurred.

In the classical music sector, a similar dynamic has been unfolding. The genre has faced barriers to accessibility and engagement, with its formal conventions and demographic skew often cited as obstacles to attracting new audiences. Yet, as this report has shown, classical music venues have gradually embraced digital tools to reimagine concert experiences. Apps, AR/VR performances, and the rising popularity of video game music concerts all point to a growing openness to engaging with classical music. These strategies not only offer novel forms of participation but also help classical music intersect with other domains of cultural engagement, especially video games, where orchestral scores and soundtracks have long played an evocative role.

The sport sector illustrates an even wider and deeper engagement with gamified innovations. Not only are immersive technologies currently explored to enhance live experiences, but sport institutions have begun to actively embrace the video game ecosystem, particularly esports and virtual platforms, as integral to their fan engagement strategies. However, this transformation is not without complexity. The uneven uptake of immersive tools, dependence on dominant digital platforms, and speculative nature of some Web3 initiatives signal that innovation alone is not sufficient. Cultural, economic, and ethical considerations remain central. Therefore, understanding these dynamics is essential for shaping inclusive, sustainable, and resonant forms of fan engagement in an increasingly hybrid media environment.

Thus, we argue that over time, and particularly following the COVID-19 pandemic, attitudes toward digital media have shifted, paving the way for a possible deeper intersection of video games and other cultural sectors. This shift not only normalised the integration of digital media into cultural experiences but also made it more appealing to audiences who had

grown increasingly accustomed to its use. Even before the pandemic, studies like Frantz's (2015) highlighted changing generational attitudes toward technology, noting that younger generations increasingly see it as a tool to make life more efficient, connected, and accessible. More recently, Bakashi (2025) described how the video game industry will soon receive its first wave of pensioner gamers, thus challenging the idea that digital engagement is only for the young. As these trends continue, cultural organisations have a unique opportunity to blend digital and live/in-situ experiences, reducing barriers and fostering deeper connections with both seasoned and emerging audiences and fans.

While considering the intersection of video games and other cultural sectors, we should be mindful that museums, classical music venues and sports have always been interactive and engaging spaces, even before the adoption of digital tools and video games. However, growing expectations for innovation, accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic, have pushed the sector to explore new forms of digital engagement that can reach broader and more diverse audiences. As this review has shown, gamification and video games offer promising ways to enhance learning, participation, and accessibility in the different cultural settings. Yet they also raise important concerns around sustainability, inclusivity, and the risk of diluting their messages and impairing their sense of authenticity. Therefore, these digital tools should perhaps be seen not as replacements for traditional practices, but as complementary methods that, when carefully designed, can enrich cultural experiences.

Moreover, we should remember not to perceive audiences and potential visitors as a homogeneous group. Though it is beyond the scope of this report, we should be mindful that people from different socio-demographic backgrounds might interact and engage differently with digital media and cultural venues. The UK'S Taking Part survey demonstrates these differences. The latest survey, covering 2023 and 2024, focused on cultural areas such as the arts (including live music), museums and galleries, and live sports. The survey found that between May 2023 and March 2024, 91% of adults in England engaged with the arts at least once. However, older adults (especially those aged 85+), Muslim and Pakistani individuals, and those who were long-term unemployed or had never worked were among the least likely to engage, while women, LGBTQ+ adults, and those in higher professional occupations showed higher levels of participation. Similar trends appeared in museum and gallery visits, which rose to 46% of adults visiting overall, although digital engagement remained low (only 13%). Chinese adults were among the most likely to visit museums, while white British adults had the lowest digital museum use. Live sports attendance also increased to 31%, with men, younger adults, white British and Jewish adults, and higher socio-economic groups most likely to attend, whereas older adults, women, and the long-term unemployed were less likely to do so. Watching sports on TV was more common, with 73% of adults tuning in, particularly for men's and women's football. Thus, despite some reports that cultural engagement is on the decline, we can see that the UK has seen significant levels of participation across cultural sectors. Nevertheless, this trend is not reflected in every community and age bracket while the interest in engaging digitally is low.

Taken together, the cases explored in this report suggest that video games and digital media can serve as powerful tools for cultural participation, education, and audience development across a variety of sectors. However, the successful integration of these tools depends not only on technological infrastructure or innovative design, but also on cultural sensitivity, thoughtful implementation, and sustained institutional support. As digital-native generations become increasingly central to cultural consumption, heritage institutions, arts organisations, and sports bodies alike will need to navigate the tension between tradition and transformation, seeking ways to meet audiences where they are, while preserving the core values and integrity of their practices.

7. REFERENCES

- Aitamurto, T., Jean-Baptiste B., Kaiping C., Ahmed C., and Skanda S. (2018). “The Impact of Augmented Reality on Art Engagement: Liking, Impression of Learning, and Distraction.” In *Virtual, Augmented and Mixed Reality: Applications in Health, Cultural Heritage, and Industry*. Edited by J. Y.C. Chen & G. Fragomeni (pp. 153–171). Springer.
- Antonelli, P., & Galloway, P. (2022). *When Video Games Came to the Museum*. The Museum of Modern Art. <https://www.moma.org/magazine/articles/798>.
- Arsenal FC. (2024). Virtual stadium tour. <https://arsenaldirect.arsenal.com/tour/virtual-stadium-tour>.
- Bagnall, G., Crawford, G., Gislam, C., Gosling, V., Simpson, S., Stukoff, M, Yodovich, N. (2024). Workshop Report. Developed by the Horizon Europe project GAMEHEARTS (Games, Heritage, Arts, & Sport: the economic, social, and cultural value of the European video game ecosystem – GAMEHEARTS), funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101132543, (106 pages).
- Bagnall, G., Light, B., Crawford, G., & Gosling, V. (2013). *The Imperial War Museum’s social interpretation project*. <https://eprints.qut.edu.au/61233>
- Bakashi, M. (2025) Industry welcomes first wave of pensioner gamers. *BBC*. Retrieved from: <https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/c861egvqlzjo>.
- Barron, P., & Leask, A. (2017). Visitor engagement at museums: Generation Y and ‘Lates’ events at the National Museum of Scotland. *Museum Management and Curatorship*, 32(5), 473-490.
- Bayle, L., & Provenzano, C. (2021). The Interface between Classical Music and Technology. *Classical Music*, 103.
- BBC. (2017). More than a third of fans watch illegal Premier League streams. *BBC Sport*. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/sport/football/40483486>
- Bogost, I. (2007). *Persuasive games*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Berger, K. (2011). Classical music waltzes with digital media. *Los Angeles Times*. Retrieved from <http://articles.latimes.com/2011/aug/07/entertainment/la-ca-classical-technology-20110807>
- Beyond (2024). OPUS – The next stage. Retrieved from: <https://beyondconference.org/b24/showcase/opus-the-next-stage/>
- BeyondGames.biz. (2024). Manchester City and Sony unveil metaverse fan engagement platform. <https://www.beyondgames.biz/20288/manchester-city-football-metaverse/>
- Bootle, E. (2019). Keep your phones on: how a new app will make classical music more accessible. *The New Statesmen*. Retrieved from: <https://www.newstatesman.com/culture/music/2019/09/keep-your-phones-how-new-app-will-make-classical-music-more-accessible>.

- Bossavit, B., Pina, A., Sanchez-Gil, I., & Urtasun, A. (2018). Educational games to enhance museum visits for schools. *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, 21(4), 171-186.
- Botstein, L. (1996). The Future of the Orchestra. *The Musical Quarterly*, 80(2), 189-193.
- Brown, A. (2004). Smart Concerts: orchestras in the age of entertainment. Knight Foundation Issues Brief Series No. 5. <https://knightfoundation.org/reports/magic-music-issues-brief-5-smart-concerts-orchestr/>
- Bruner, R. (2021). The livestream show will go on: How COVID has changed live music—forever. *Time*. <https://time.com/5950135/livestream-music-future/>
- Camps-Ortueta, Irene, Luis Deltell-Escolar, and María-Francisca Blasco-López. “New technology in Museums: AR and VR video games are coming.” *Communication & Society* (2021), 193-210.
- Carling, C., Reilly, T., & Williams, A. M. (2009). *Performance Assessment for Field Sports*. Routledge.
- Carlsson, R. (2020). How can museums use gaming to their advantage? *MuseumNext*. <https://www.museumnext.com/article/how-can-museums-use-gaming-to-their-advantage/>
- Çetin, Ö., & Erbay, F. (2021). Gamification practices in museums. *Journal of Tourismology*, 7(2), 265-276.
- Chung, J. (11 March 2024). The day the music dies? Why time is running out to tackle the decline in UK music education. Retrieved from: <https://www.rncm.ac.uk/news/the-day-the-music-dies-why-time-is-running-out-to-tackle-the-decline-in-uk-music-education/>
- Coates, C. (2025). Premier League: TV viewing figures down on Sky Sports and TNT Sports. *BBC News*. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/articles/cp3n7dx2174o>
- Connor, A. (2025). In real life: Gaming community engagement in museums. *Curator: The Museum Journal*, 68(1), 9-22.
- Crawford, G., & Gosling, V. K. (2009). More than a game: Sports-themed video games & player narratives. *Sociology of Sport Journal*, 26(1), 50–66.
- Crawford, G., Fenton, A., Chadwick, S., & Lawrence, S. (2022). All Avatars Aren't We: Football and the experience of football-themed digital content during a global pandemic. *International Review for the Sociology of Sport*, 57(4), 515–531. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10126902211022601>
- Crawford, G., Gosling, V., Bagnall, G., & Light, B. (2014). An orchestral audience: Classical music and continued patterns of distinction. *Cultural Sociology*, 8(4), 483-500.
- Crawford, G. (2006). The cult of Champ Man: The culture and pleasures of Championship Manager/Football Manager gamers. *Information, Communication & Society*, 9(4), 496–514.

- Culture, Media and Sport Committee. (2023). *NFTs and the blockchain: The risks to sport and culture* (House of Commons, HC 598). UK Parliament. <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm5803/cmselect/cmcmds/598/report.html>
- Dapper Labs. (2021). LaLiga joins forces with Dapper Labs to launch an all-new digital collectible experience for football fans around the globe. *Dapper Labs*. <https://www.dapperlabs.com/newsroom/laliga-joins-forces-with-dapper-labs-to-launch-an-all-new-digital-collectible-experience-for-football-fans-around-the-globe>
- Djaouti, D., Alvarez, J., Jessel, J. P., & Rampnoux, O. (2011). Origins of serious games. *Serious games and edutainment applications*, 25-43.
- DFL. (2025a, April 25). An immersive glimpse into the future. *DFL*. <https://www.dfl.de/en/innovation/an-immersive-glimpse-into-the-future/>
- DFL. (2025b, August 9). Augmented reality: The immersive football experience. *DFL*. <https://www.dfl.de/en/innovation/augmented-reality-the-immersive-football-experience/>
- Dobson, M. C. (2010). New audiences for classical music: The experiences of non-attenders at live orchestral concerts. *Journal of New Music Research*, 39(2), 111-124.
- FC Business. (2024). Engaging a new generation of fans through games. *FC Business*. <https://fcbusiness.co.uk/interviews-features/engaging-a-new-generation-of-fans-through-games/>
- Frantz, E. L. (2015). *Is technology the way forward for classical music? Exploring audience engagement in the digital era* (Master's thesis, The Ohio State University).
- Fraser, G. (2025). Football and other premium TV being pirated at 'industrial scale'. *BBC News*. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/articles/cp3n7dx2174o>
- Fox, M. A., Breese, J. L., & Vaidyanathan, G. (2019). Live music performances and the internet of things. *Issues in Information Systems, International Association for Computer Information Systems*, 23 (3), pp.179-188.
- Gibbons, W. (2018). *Unlimited replays : Video games and classical music*. Oxford University Press
- Gibson, O. (2016). Is the unthinkable happening – are people finally switching the football off?. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/football/2016/oct/24/sky-sports-bt-sport-people-switching-football-off>
- Gislam, C., Bagnall, G., Crawford, G., Gosling, V. (2025). Do Video Games Matter? Examining Video Games' Pathways to Legitimacy and Cultural Value Through Cultural Intermediaries. *Games and Culture*.
- Gregory, S. (2016). Virtual Reality Could Change the Way You Watch Sports. *Time*. <https://time.com/4458601/virtual-reality-nba-nextvr/>
- Gregory, S. (2016). Virtual reality is isolating, expensive and awkward – but it might still win. *Time*. <https://time.com>

- Guttman, A. (1978). *From Ritual to Record: The Nature of Modern Sports*. Columbia University Press.
- Hanquinet, L & Savage, M. (2012) 'Educative leisure' and the art museum', *Museum and Society*, 10(1), 42-59.
- Hernández, J.C. (2023). Apple's New App Aims to Make Classical Music More Accessible. *New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2023/04/02/arts/music/apple-music-classical-streaming.html>
- Illsley, W. R., Almevik, G., Westin, J., Aavaranta Hansén, J. B., Fornander, E., Hallgren, E., Lagercrantz, W., & Vasileiou, P. (2025). The edutainment scan: immersive media and its deployment in museums. *Museum Management and Curatorship*, 40(1), 18-35.
- Immersiv.io. (2023). DFL Supercup ARISE broadcast. *Immersiv.io*. <https://www.immersiv.io/portfolio/dfi-supercup-arise-broadcast/>
- Ingle, S. (2017). Sport 2.0: crumbling traditions create a whole new ball game. Sport 2.0, *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/sport/2017/jun/13/traditional-sports-crisis-sport-2-0>
- IWM. (2022). *NOW OPEN: War Games at IWM London, the UK's first exhibition to explore what video games tell us about conflict* [Press Release]. Imperial War Museums.
- James, D. A. (2013). A Structured Approach for Technology Innovation in Sport. *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, 8(1), 253–264.
- Janssen, S., Katz-Gerro, T., Jörg, J., Cvetičanin, P. & Verboord. M. (2021). *Policy Brief I*. Retrieved from: <https://inventculture.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/policy-brief-complete.pdf>.
- Jenkins, T. (2017). How Football is Adapting to the Demands of the Digital World. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/football/video/2017/jun/14/how-football-is-adapting-to-the-demands-of-the-digital-world-video-sport-2-0>
- Jones, J. (2012). Sorry MoMA, video games are not art. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/artanddesign/jonathanjonesblog/2012/nov/30/moma-video-games-art>.
- Kidd, J. (2015). Gaming for affect: Museum online games and the embrace of empathy. *Journal of curatorial studies*, 4(3), 414-432.
- Kolb, B.M. (2000). 'You Call This Fun? Reactions of young, first-time attendees to a classical concert', in D. Weissman (ed.), *Music Industry Issues and Studies*, 1 (1), Music & Entertainment Industry Educators Association, New Orleans, Loyola University Press, pp.13-28.
- LaLiga. (2023). Sportian – Leading the digital transformation of sports and entertainment. *LaLiga*. <https://www.laliga.com/en-GB/laliga-tech>

- Lawrence, S., & Crawford, G. (2019). Football 2.0: Exposing and exploring the digital football fan. In S. Lawrence & G. Crawford (Eds.), *Digital Football Cultures* (pp. 186–204). Routledge.
- Lawrence, S., & Crawford, G. (Eds.). (2019). *Digital Football Cultures: Fandom, Identities and Resistance*. Routledge.
- Levy, S. (2024, February 12). This massive screen for live sports puts you in the best seat in the stadium. *Wired*. <https://www.wired.com/story/cosm-live-sports-immersive-experiences>
- MacDonald, K. (2018). Was that a reference to Magritte? Video games: Design/ Play/ Disrupt review. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/games/2018/sep/05/was-that-a-reference-to-magritte-design-play-disrupt-review>.
- MacNamara, M. (2015). Terms of engagement: Yes, audiences want classical music apps. *San Francisco Classical Voice*. Retrieved from: <https://www.sfcv.org/articles/feature/terms-engagement-yes-audiences-want-classical-music-apps>.
- Manchester.ac.uk. (2023). Black Fell: Combining gaming and opera for a compelling effect. <https://www.manchester.ac.uk/about/news/black-fell-combining-gaming-and-opera-for-a-compelling-effect/>
- Mancity.com. (2024). Manchester City has today announced the launch of the ‘Man City Virtual Etihad Stadium’. <https://www.mancity.com/news/club/manchester-city-sony-virtual-etihad-stadium-fan-experience-63859393>
- Massey, C. (2021). Discovering the second stage: Orchestras’ digital adaptation. Retrieved from: <https://amt-lab.org/blog/2021/6/discovering-the-second-stage-orchestras-digital-adaptation>.
- Marsilio, J. (2017). As cited in Raymond, A. (2017). The NBA is bringing VR basketball to fans. *The Verge*. <https://www.theverge.com>
- McMaster, M. J. (2023). *Videogames and the public museum: Six months behind the scenes* (Doctoral dissertation, RMIT University).
- Meta. (2023). UFC Fight Pass VR comes to Meta Quest. *Meta*. <https://www.meta.com/blog/ufc>
- Miah, A. (2004). *Genetically Modified Athletes: Biomedical Ethics, Gene Doping and Sport*. Routledge.
- Microsoft. (2022). LaLiga scores with fans using Microsoft Azure. <https://www.microsoft.com/en/customers/story/1655714713994650971-laliga-media-and-entertainment-microsoft-azure>
- Millers (2024, August 23). Generation z and the resurgence of classical music. *Microsoft*. https://millersmusic.co.uk/blogs/blog/generation-z-and-the-resurgence-of-classical-music?srsltid=AfmBOoqlZsE-JzILiw04JY4gB8wxLJAhr4xSPeW_Vuv92xXIkBbvzGgd

- Ministry of Sport. (2025, June 25). Premier League domestic viewership declines ahead of new broadcast cycle. <https://ministryofsport.com/premier-league-domestic-viewership-declines-ahead-of-new-broadcast-cycle/>
- MLB. (2023). MLB unveils new virtual ballpark to offer fans immersive experience. <https://www.mlb.com/press-release/press-release-mlb-unveils-new-virtual-ballpark-to-offer-fans-immersive-experienc>
- Morris Hargreaves McIntyre (2022). Conducting a thorough study of London's market for live classical music. <https://www.mhminsight.com/client-stories/conducting-a-thorough-study-of-londons-market-for-live-classical-music/>
- Naskali, T., Suominen, J., & Saarikoski, P. (2013). The introduction of computer and video games in museums—experiences and possibilities. In *Making the History of Computing Relevant: IFIP WG 9.7 International Conference, HC 2013, London, UK, June 17-18, 2013, Revised Selected Papers* (pp. 226-245). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- Nieborg, D. B., & Poell, T. (2021). *Platforms and cultural production*. Polity Press.
- Nielsen Sports. (2022, February 23). Fans are changing the game: 2022 Global Sports Marketing Report. *Nielsen Sports*. <https://niensensports.com/fans-are-changing-the-game-2022-global-sports-marketing-report/>
- Nofal, E., Panagiotidou, G., Reffat, R. M., Hameeuw, H., Boschloos, V., & Vande Moere, A. (2020). Situated tangible gamification of heritage for supporting collaborative learning of young museum visitors. *Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage (JOCCH)*, 13(1), 1-24.
- Orlovsky, D. (2024, February 4). Virtual play breakdowns on NFL Live. *ESPN*. <https://www.espn.com>
- O'Sullivan, T. (2009). All together now: A symphony orchestra audience as a consuming community. *Consumption, Markets and Culture*, 12(3), 209-223.
- Phillips, M., & Krause, A. E. (2024). Audiences of the Future—How Can Streamed Music Performance Replicate the Live Music Experience?. In N. T. Smith, P. Peters, & K. Molina (eds.), *Classical Music Futures: Practices of Innovation* (pp. 333-354). Cambridge: Open Book Publishers.
- Raimo, N., De Turi, I., Ricciardelli, A., & Vitolla, F. (2022). Digitalization in the cultural industry: evidence from Italian museums. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 28(8), 1962-1974.
- Raymond, A. (2017, October 25). The NBA is bringing VR basketball to fans. *The Verge*. <https://www.theverge.com>
- Raymond, A. K. (2017). Soon Virtual Reality Will Let Everyone Attend the Super Bowl. *NBC News*. <https://www.nbcnews.com/mach/innovation/virtual-reality-major-sports-are-bringing-stadium-you-n716506>

- RSL Communications. (2023, August 8). RSL enters the metaverse with Boom Interactive. *Real Salt Lake*. <https://www.rsl.com/news/rsl-enters-metaverse-with-boom-interactive-inc>
- Royal Philharmonic Orchestra (2023). *A time to look forward: Trends of engagement with orchestral music*. Retrieved from: https://www.rpo.co.uk/images//articles/2023_Insights_Report/RPO_Insights_Report_2022_release.pdf.
- Sangamuang, S., Wongwan, N., Intawong, K., Khanchai, S., & Puritat, K. (2025). Gamification in Virtual Reality Museums: Effects on Hedonic and Eudaimonic Experiences in Cultural Heritage Learning. *Informatics*, 12(1), 27. <https://doi.org/10.3390/informatics12010027>
- Sánchez-Amboage, E., Enrique Membiela-Pollán, M., Martínez-Fernández, V. A., & Molinillo, S. (2023). Tourism marketing in a metaverse context: the new reality of European museums on meta. *Museum Management and Curatorship*, 38(4), 468-489.
- Schultz, C. K. N. (2023). Creating the ‘virtual’ witness: The limits of empathy. *Museum Management and Curatorship*, 38(1), 2-17.
- Sigurjonsson, N. (2010). Orchestra audience development and the aesthetics of “customer comfort”. *The Journal of Arts Management, Law, and Society*, 40,266-278.
- Small, C. (1987). Performance as ritual: sketch for an enquiry into the true nature of a symphony concert’, in A.L White (ed.) *Lost in Music: culture, Style and the musical event*. London: Routledge.
- Taking part (2025, February 13). *Main report for the Participation Survey (May 2023 to March 2024)*. <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/participation-survey-2023-24-annual-publication/main-report-for-the-participation-survey-may-2023-to-march-2024>
- Taylor, L. (2025, June 26). Mainstream TV audiences for Women’s Super League dropped 35% last season. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/football/2025/jun/26/mainstream-tv-audiences-for-womens-super-league-dropped-35-last-season>
- UEFA. (2024a). Atos to deliver key IT services and applications for UEFA EURO 2024. <https://www.uefa.com/insideuefa/news/028b-1a3d944f99f4-84f2a02c5f6e-1000-atos-to-deliver-key-it-services-for-euro-2024/>
- UEFA. (2024b). UEFA Innovation Hub. <https://www.uefa.com/development/our-support/innovation-hub/>
- V&A. (2024). *About us* · V&A. Victoria and Albert Museum. <https://www.vam.ac.uk/info/about-us>.
- Watch.NBA.com. (2023). Watch NBA games in VR on Meta Quest. <https://watch.nba.com>
- Wright, O. (2017). Sky Sports loses quarter of audience in five years. *The Times*. <https://www.thetimes.co.uk/article/sky-sports-loses-quarter-of-audience-in-five-years-k8z3f2kvs>

- Xu, C., & Fagan, T. (2023). Empowering Learners through the Integration of Museum Experiences and Digital Technologies. *Museum Worlds*, 11(1), 181-191.
- Yodovich, N., Bagnall, G., Crawford, G., Gislam, C., Stukoff, M. (2025). Video games in/as culture: The evolving cultural significance of video games. *International Journal of the Sociology of Leisure*.
- Zhang, J., Zhu, T., & Chang, X. (2024). Educational Games of Museums: A Literature Review. *Games and Culture*, 15554120241270058.
- Zhou, Y., Chen, J., & Wang, M. (2022). A meta-analytic review on incorporating virtual and augmented reality in museum learning. *Educational Research Review*, 36, 100454.

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